

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF ADMINISTRATIVE EMPOWERMENT BETWEEN TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES IN THE YEMEN RED SEA PORTS CORPORATION, REPUBLIC OF YEMEN

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Abstract

The study aimed to support the organizational citizenship behavior of employees at the Yemen Red Sea Ports Corporation by defining the role of administrative empowerment as a mediator in the impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior. The study relied on the quantitative approach, and the study sample was chosen using the relative stratified random sampling method, which amounted to (291) individuals. The data of the study were obtained from the distribution of questionnaires and analyzed using the structural equation modeling (Smart-PLS-SEM). The study revealed that transformational leadership and administrative empowerment directly affect the behavior of organizational citizenship, and that leadership transformational directly affects administrative empowerment, and that administrative empowerment represents a partial mediator in the impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Administrative Empowerment, Organizational Citizenship Behavior

INTRODUCTION

The various economic, political, social, and technical developments have led to rapid changes and intense competition in the environment of business organizations, forcing them to pay increasing attention to the human element at the functional and organizational levels. In order to ensure survival, continuity, and growth.

The human element is considered one of the most important resources of business organizations and a fundamental pillar due to the various interactional patterns that create them and through which the effectiveness and efficiency of these organizations can be judged (Abuzaid, 2018, p. 641). Organizational citizenship behavior is considered a relatively recent concept in organizational thought, as it has received great attention from researchers and thinkers because it focuses on the human element, which is one of the organization's most important resources (Alsharah, 2018, p. 587). The success of organizations depends on employees who go beyond their official roles and race to provide the best and exceed expected performance (Robbins & Judge, 2015), and organizations that have employees who have good organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) will have better performance than other organizations (Al-Gharabiya, 2019). The organizational citizenship behavior of employees is behavior that goes beyond the requirements of an individual's official role (Taseer et al., 2020). Therefore, striving towards studying organizational citizenship behavior contributes to enhancing organizational effectiveness, helps to increase and maximize functional

and organizational performance, and affects the success of the organization (Yaghmour et al., 2018, p. 603).

Many recent studies have indicated the effectiveness of the transformational style for all organizations in light of contemporary conditions due to its association with most organizational variables such as job satisfaction, organizational performance, organizational trust, organizational citizenship behaviors, organizational commitment, and organizational culture (Kshirsagar & Ramgade, 2021; Nugraha et al., 2021; Abu Al-Saud, 2020; Ghadi, 2017). Moreover, transformational leadership becomes an important element in the organization to gain a better understanding of motivating employees and determining their attitudes and behaviors (Nathani et al., 2020, p. 119).

Steinmann et al. (2018) showed that transformational leadership is a personal behavior that aims to not only increase followers' levels of motivation but also increase job satisfaction and generate a sense of competence, self-worth, and job commitment. The transformational leader has the ability to influence the behavior of others and motivate them, which contributes to the effectiveness and success of organizational goals (Overton & Putra, 2021, p. 24). Burns (1978) is considered the first to formulate the idea of the transformational leadership style, through which the theory of transformational leadership was crystallized. Then other researchers, such as Bass (1985) and Avolio et al. (1988), came to develop and refine Burns' idea. Transformational leaders are described as visionaries who have the ability to change and improve by instilling loyalty and belonging to ensure greater loyalty to their leadership. Transformational leaders instill complete satisfaction among followers, which motivates them to perform additional behaviors (Majeed et al., 2017, p. 572).

Administrative empowerment is one of the methods that affect the behavior of organizational citizenship (Mohamed & Al-Sayed, 2020), which is known as the optimal investment of the human element because of its major role in motivating workers, unleashing their latent energies in carrying out the organization's work, and increasing the process of communication between workers and the organization (Alsharah, 2018, p. 581). In addition, it represents one of the basic strategies for organizations to confront various changes, challenges, and developments (Abuzaid 2018, p. 641).

Many previous studies have confirmed the existence of a close relationship between transformational leadership and administrative empowerment (Tania et al., 2021; Ayed & Al-Qahfah, 2020; Yildirim & Nktuk, 2017). This relationship indicates that transformational leadership works to empower their workforce by matching the goals and objectives of subordinates, the leader, the group, and the organization (Ibrahim et al., 2017, p. 2).

In this context, transformational leadership, administrative empowerment, and organizational citizenship behavior become important behaviors for achieving organizational goals efficiently and effectively.

The maritime transport sector is considered one of the most important economic sectors in Yemen because of its great importance in bringing about development and strengthening the national economy in various circumstances, as the Yemeni Red Sea Ports Corporation represents 70% of the total marine revenues (Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, 2020, p. 15), and as a result of the impact of political, economic, and social factors due to the crisis the country is going through, the Yemeni Red Sea Ports Corporation, like other Yemeni organizations, has witnessed

challenges, intense competition, and a rapid change in its environment, which negatively affected its available resources and capabilities.

From the above, leaders in the organization must practice transformational leadership and benefit from its positive impact in supporting organizational citizenship behavior among employees, especially if they are empowered as strategic inputs to enhance the ability to deal with crises and challenges facing their organizations. According to the library survey, it was found that there is a research gap, as the two researchers did not stop at a study that dealt with the mediating role of administrative empowerment in the impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior in the Yemeni, Arab, and foreign environments and in the maritime transport sector, and this represented a motivation for the researchers to study this subject through a field study conducted in the Yemen Red Sea Ports Corporation, northwest of Yemen.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

During the past few decades, interest in studying organizational citizenship behavior has increased in the field of administrative sciences (Khan et al., 2022, p. 1195). The main reason for this is the belief that organizational citizenship behavior may lead to greater organizational effectiveness and success (Kiyani et al., 2019, p. 156).

At the outset, a distinction must be made between formal role behavior and auxiliary role behavior. Dane et al. defined formal role behavior as behavior that is required or expected as part of the assigned duties of a job. As for additional role behavior, it expresses appreciative behavior that benefits the organization and exceeds the expectations of the current role. Organizational citizenship behavior is a form of additive role behavior (Yaghmour et al., 2018, p. 607). One of the most cited definitions of OCB is Organ's (1988, p. 4): "as individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization". Appreciative behavior means that it is not part of the employee's official duties (Nugraha et al., 2021, p. 2436), which may not be recognized by the leader or rewarded informally, and this may represent a defect in organizational citizenship behavior. If employees believe they are not being treated fairly in times of crisis, there is an urgent need for the leader's support for them (Murtezaj & Ahmeti, 2021, p. 95).

Transformational Leadership (TL)

Transformational leadership (TL) has emerged as one of the contemporary leadership methods for realizing individual, group, and organizational effectiveness (Ghadi, 2017, p. 144).

Transformational leadership theory is often talked about as a "new paradigm" or a "new leadership" tactic (Majeed et al., 2017, p. 573). According to Samodra et al. (2021, p. 1353), this paradigm focuses much of its attention on the charismatic and inspirational aspects of the leader. According to Robbins and Judge, transformational leadership is defined as the extent to which a leader inspires his followers and motivates them to transcend their self-interests and his ability to have a significant impact on their behavior (Jaya et al., 2021, p. 5). Transformational leadership demonstrates that leaders boost the interest of their employees by highlighting their

grasp of the group's mission and vision and advancing the group's interests (Ibrahim et al., 2017, p. 3). At the same time, Bass and Riggio stated that transformational leadership can excite and motivate subordinates to exceed expected performance, as transformational leaders motivate others to do more than they aim for and even more than they thought possible, which may contribute to high levels of subordinate satisfaction and commitment to the group (Yaghmour et al., 2018). Bass took into account that transformational leaders seek to motivate their subordinates to go beyond basic requirements and focus on the organization's mission and vision. As a result, followers will be creative and make significant contributions to the work environment (Ghadi, 2017, p. 147).

Transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior

Transformational leadership (TL) has emerged as one of the predominant leadership approaches to understanding individual, group, and organizational effectiveness (Zhang et al., 2020, p. 469). In the past few years, a large number of studies have been conducted on transformational leadership and its relationship to a variety of outcomes (Tian et al., 2020, p. 3). Previous studies indicated that transformational leadership significantly affects the behavior of organizational citizenship (Nugraha et al., 2021; Abu Al-Saud, 2020; Al-Gharabiya, 2019; Yaghmour et al., 2018). Transformational leadership, according to Nathani et al. (2021, p. 128), is more strongly associated with organizational citizenship behavior, both directly and indirectly. When leaders display transformational leadership traits, it is believed to influence follower behavior because followers feel confident and appreciative of their leader and are motivated to accomplish more than what is officially asked of them (Jayarathna, 2019, p. 4). According to Bryant, transformational leaders foster a climate conducive to generating, sharing, and exploring knowledge through the qualities of inspirational motivation and individual consideration (Majeed et al., 2017, p. 576). Such leaders also care about the needs of their followers, work to satisfy them, and increase their level of motivation to reach their fullest potential (Zhang et al., 2020, p. 469). In addition, Bass (1990) stated that when leaders direct attention and appreciation toward the organizational task, it motivates employees to go above and beyond expectations. Employees begin to look beyond their own interests for the benefit of the organization. Transformational leadership also sets a clear collective vision through which followers work to transcend their self-interest, as transformational leadership is shown to have a significant impact on positive work-related outcomes (Jayarathna, 2019, p. 4). Bass also found that transformational leadership is a level of exchange of values and ethics between the leader and the subordinate that transforms the values of the subordinate into performance that exceeds the expectations of what is formally prescribed to achieve organizational goals (Boamah et al., 2018, p. 181). We can hypothesize that:

H1: There is a statistically significant effect of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior.

Administrative Empowerment (AE)

With the onset of the 21st century, the traditional role of management, based on hierarchy and central authority, began to slow down, opening the way for more democratic methods or participatory management (Al Naggat, 2022, p. 194). The basic concept of the new management methods is empowerment, which encourages teamwork, participation in decision-making, and concern for subordinates (Abou

Elnaga & Imran, 2014, p. 14). There is no consensus among researchers about the definition and practices of empowerment (Abun et al., 2021, p. 14). Overton and Putra (2021, p. 24) define it as an administrative practice that aims to motivate employees, increase their involvement in the decision-making process, and give better options to employees to improve their performance, provide distinguished services to customers, and achieve goals. Vasanth and Udayasuriyan (2021, p. 3123) stated that empowering employees increases employees' satisfaction with their jobs and leads to better performance in their work. According to Ayed and Al-Qahfah (2020, p. 31), It is to grant employees full powers related to their work to increase their ability to make decisions on their own without referring to senior management. Thus, administrative empowerment is a concept that focuses on human resources, strengthens the relationship between the leader and subordinates, gives confidence to subordinates in performing their work, makes them responsible, and develops their capabilities that enable them to acquire skills and knowledge in decision-making and problem-solving (Alsharah, 2018, p. 586).

Transformational leadership and administrative empowerment

Administrative empowerment is one of the basic features of transformational leadership, which is characterized by following methods and behaviors that encourage employee empowerment, such as delegating responsibilities, enhancing the capabilities of subordinates to think for themselves, and encouraging them to put forward innovative and creative ideas (Khairy, 2014, p. 190). Employees believe in empowerment in the performance of their work, feel highly confident with others, and are ready to achieve success by continuing to learn and develop in their roles. Employee behavior changes for the better and is more likely to lead to positive results when they view their workplace as providing opportunities rather than placing restrictions on them (Jayarathna, 2019, p. 4). Abu Mustafa (2021, p. 143) indicates that transformational leadership empowers subordinates, develops their skills, and enhances their self-confidence. It also works to create self-reliant groups and work teams, in addition to bringing about a fundamental change in the behavior of subordinates and their values. According to Bass and Riggio, transformational leaders respond to the individual needs of their subordinates, develop their leadership skills, help them grow, motivate them, and inspire them to achieve positive results in the process by empowering them (Ibrahim et al., 2017, p. 5). According to Prakasa and Astuty (2022, p. 817), the presence of transformational leadership may have a positive impact on the administrative empowerment of employees. Effective transformational leadership works to meet the needs of employees and increase their potential. Several previous studies were conducted by Overton and Putra (2021), Ayed and Al-Qahfah (2020), and Yildirim and Nktuk (2017), which showed the positive impact of the transformational leadership style on enabling employees to perform their work and at the level of jobs that include a number of individuals, departments, and divisions. All of which mean the direct impact between transformational leadership and administrative empowerment at the functional and organizational levels. We can assume that:

H2: There is a statistically significant effect of transformational leadership on empowerment administrative.

Administrative empowerment and organizational citizenship behavior

It has been exposed that organizational factors play a vital role in supporting organizational citizenship behavior among employees (Khan et al., 2022, p. 1196). One such factor that can affect OCB is the managerial empowerment of employees (Abun et al., 2021).

When it comes to the successful operation of an organization, there is a need for employees who can take the initiative to go beyond their job requirements, such as engaging in organizational citizenship behavior. This is why empowerment has attracted so much attention (Zhong et al., 2011, p. 614). Empowerment increases employees' sense of control and prompts them to engage more in performing their work (Jeong et al., 2019, p. 6). Many recent studies that use the direct influence approach have realized the effect of empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior, such as the study of Afram et al. (2022), Tania et al. (2021), and Alsharah (2018). These studies showed that employee empowerment through delegation of authority, work teams, training, and motivation leads to increased practices of organizational citizenship behavior. We can hypothesize that:

H3: There is a statistically significant effect of administrative empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior.

Administrative empowerment as a mediator

To our knowledge, no previous studies have revealed the mediating effect of managerial empowerment between transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior. However, some studies indicate that leaders, when they practice the correct transformation of behavior ("ideal influence, inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration"), increase the empowerment of subordinates in managing their jobs efficiently and effectively (Abu Mustafa, 2021; Ayed & Al-Qahfah, 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2017). Moreover, Al-Gharabiya (2019) found that organizational citizenship behavior is directly affected by both transformational leadership and managerial empowerment.

The leadership literature and research are consistent with the concept of leadership theories, specifically the transformational leadership theory, according to Burns (1978). The transformational leadership theory focuses on mutual understanding between leaders and followers, and links between them raise the level of motivation and ethics. Leaders work according to this concept by meeting the needs of subordinates and supporting them to reach their fullest potential. According to Bass (1985), transformational leadership theory assumes that the interaction between leaders and followers, by inspiring followers to go beyond their own interests, supports the interests of the organization. The application of these theories within the framework of organizational leadership shows that all qualities that are characterized by a high degree of principles, values, and ethics can advance the organization and its development if transformational leadership motivates employees to do more than what is expected by raising the level of awareness of followers of the importance and value of specific and ideal goals, paying attention to individual differences among them, developing their abilities, and motivating them to think beyond their own interests for the benefit of the organization. If implemented properly, these transformational processes will further empower followers to perform their jobs efficiently and effectively, which may lead to greater organizational citizenship behavior. We can hypothesize that:

H4: Administrative empowerment mediates the effect of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior.

Figure (1) shows the cognitive model of the study.

Figure 1: The cognitive model of the study

METHODOLOGY

This study used the quantitative method. As the most suitable research method for testing the hypotheses of the study.

Study population and sample

The study population is represented by the Yemeni Red Sea Ports Corporation in the Republic of Yemen, which constitutes the transportation sector in Yemen, which is considered one of the important economic sectors. The sample of the study using the proportional stratified random sampling method is 291 individuals from the study population, which is an appropriate percentage for a study population of 1200 according to the formula (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

A total of 335 questionnaires were distributed after calculating the probability of not returning some questionnaires to ensure the return of a number of questionnaires equal to or close to the sample size. (291) questionnaires were retrieved, meaning (86.87%) of the total questionnaire distributed.

At a rate of (100%) of the total sample size of the study, and therefore the number of questionnaires that were subjected to analysis was (289) questionnaires, at a rate of (99.31%) of the total sample size.

Analysis unit

The unit of analysis for this study was the individuals (supervisor and subordinate) in the organization, because the variables of the study were based on the level of individuals.

Instrumentation

The questionnaire was constructed based on a seven-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 7 = “strongly agree.”

1. Citizenship Behavior Organizational: used a 22-item scale based on the Apparatus (1988) model.
2. Transformational Leadership: A 17-item scale developed by Bass and Riggio (2006) based on the model of Bass and Avolio (1994) was taken.
3. Administrative Empowerment: This study used a scale created by Mohamed and Al-Sayed (2020), Ayed and Al-Qahfah (2020), and Abu Mustafa (2021), consisting of 17 elements.

Table 1: The values of reliability and validity indicators

Variables	Items no.	Alpha Cronpa	Composite stability	Explained mean variance
OCB	22	0.908	0.934	0.764
TL	17	0.837	0.932	0.768
AE	17	0.901	0.930	0.761

OCB: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, TL: Transformational Leadership, AE: Administrative Empowerment

From the table, it is clear that each of the composite stability and the value of the Cronbach’s Alpha value is greater than (0.700) and less than (0.950), and this indicates that the variables are characterized by stability and internal consistency. As for the indicators of validity and convergence by measuring the mean of the extracted variance for each variable greater than 50%, this means the validity of these tools for all field study data and their use in conducting hypothesis testing analyses.

Data analysis

The data were processed statistically using a program using structural equation modeling for the social sciences (Smart-PLS4-SEM).

Hypothesis testing and discussion

Measuring the direct effect between transformational leadership and OCB

Table 2: Hypothesis 01

Variables	Standard Beta	Standard error	T Statistics	P-value
TL→OCB	0.711	0.035	20.268	0.000

From Table (2), it is clear that there is a statistically significant effect (of transformational leadership) on organizational citizenship behavior, where the beta value was (0.711) and the t value was (20.268) statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.05, and this indicates that when the level of transformational leadership increases by 100%, the level of organizational citizenship behavior increases by 71.1%, and therefore we accept hypothesis H1.

This result is shows by leaders motivating subordinates to go beyond their personal interests for the benefit of their organization, clarifying the future vision and common goals between them, paying attention to their individual needs, listening to their opinions and suggestions, and helping them think in innovative ways to address the problems they face. This in turn enhances the organizational citizenship behavior of employees. This result is consistent with the several previous studies (Nugraha et al.,

2021; Tania et al., 2021; Nathani et al., 2021; Jayarathna, 2019; Al-Gharabiya, 2019; Yaghmour et al., 2018; Abu Al-Saud, 2020; Majeed et al., 2017).

Measuring the direct effect between transformational leadership and administrative empowerment

Table 3: Hypothesis 02

Variables	Beta	Standard error	T Statistics	P-value
TL→AE	0.921	0.008	109.98	0.000

From Table (3), it is clear that there is a statistically significant effect of transformational leadership on administrative empowerment, where the beta value was 0.921 and the t value was 109.98, both statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.05. This indicates that when the level of transformational leadership increases by 100%, the level of administrative empowerment increases by 92.1%, and therefore we accept hypothesis H2.

This result shows that increasing transformational leadership in the organization leads to increased empowerment and enhances the empowering capabilities of employees, meaning that transformational leaders are able to enable their subordinates to perform their roles at work by delegating authority to subordinates, involving them in decision-making, spreading the spirit of teamwork, and supporting their capabilities. Whenever attention is paid to this, it will result in an increase in the employees' sense of empowerment. This result is consistent with the several studies (Abu Mustafa, 2021; Overton & Putra, 2021; Ayed & Al-Qahfah, 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2017).

Measuring the direct effect between administrative empowerment and organizational citizenship behavior

Table 4: Hypothesis 03

Variables	Beta	Standard error	T Statistics	P-value
AE→OCB	0.716	0.037	19.166	0.000

From Table (4), it is clear that there is a statistically significant effect of administrative empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior, where the beta value was (0.716) and the t value was (19.166), both statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.05. This indicates that when the level of administrative empowerment is increased by 100%, the level of organizational citizenship behavior increases by 71.6%, and therefore we accept hypothesis H3.

This result shows that by distributing powers to all administrative levels, creating a high degree of empowerment climate for work teams instead of focusing on individual performance, providing equal training opportunities for all employees, and providing an incentive system that is compatible with their aspirations, the greater the interest in these matters, the more Practice. Employees organizational citizenship behavior. This result is consistent with the study (Afram et al., 2022; Al Fadhal et al., 2021; Hamawandy et al., 2021; Abun et al., 2021; Mohamed & Al-Sayed, 2020; Alsharah, 2018; Zhong et al., 2011).

Measuring the effect of administrative empowerment as a mediator

Table 5: Hypothesis 04

Variables	Beta	Standard error	T Statistics	P-value
TL→ AE→ OCB	0.387	0.098	3.929	0.000

From Table (5), it is clear that there is a statistically significant mediating effect (of administrative empowerment) between transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior, where the beta value was (0.387) and the t value was (3.929), statistically significant at a significance level less than 0.05, and this means that empowerment Administrative empowerment is a mechanism to transfer the indirect impact of transformational leadership to organizational citizenship behavior, meaning that 0.38.7% of the total impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior passes through administrative empowerment, and therefore we accept hypothesis H4 for the study. This result shows that when the leaders in the organization practice the transformational leadership method correctly, employees will feel empowered, and when empowered, they will generate feelings of loyalty and belonging to their organization through organizational citizenship behavior practices. This result is consistent with transformational leadership theory that was used to prove the hypothesis. H4.

Theoretical and practical implications

The results of the study resulted in some implications at the theoretical and practical levels, which can be highlighted as follows:

Theoretical contribution

This study contributes to bridging the research gaps in the literature related to transformational leadership, managerial empowerment, and organizational citizenship behavior by providing scientific evidence for the links between these concepts. This study also responds to the study of Yaghmour et al. (2018), which suggested conducting other studies linking transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior with other variables and in sectors other than the banking sector.

Practical implications

This study provides a real vision for the management of the Yemen Red Sea Ports Corporation to enhance the organizational citizenship behavior of employees through the application of transformational leadership and the orientation towards the practice of administrative empowerment of employees by their supervisors to enable them to perform additional roles that are not required of them that contribute to the success of the institution in its ability to Dealing with crises and challenges, the results of the study help the organization's management in addressing the deficiencies in the current administrative practices by leaders and supervisors because negative practices lead to a decrease in job satisfaction, which in turn can lead to a decrease in the organizational citizenship behavior of employees. The results of the study provide a vision for the institution about establishing a culture of empowerment for administrative staff because of its role in highlighting voluntary and informal participation among employees.

CONCLUSION

Through the results of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a direct effect between transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior as a result of applying the correct behavior of the transformational leadership style.
2. Transformational leadership directly affects administrative empowerment, and therefore the correct behavior of transformational leadership supports the process of administrative empowerment.
3. Administrative empowerment directly affects organizational citizenship behavior, and therefore the empowerment process enhances organizational citizenship behavior.
4. Administrative empowerment partially mediates the impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior and thus helps support the direct impact of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the conclusions, the study recommends the following

1. The need for the organization's leadership to pay attention to the positive practices of the transformational leadership style at all administrative levels and its significant impact on the employees' practice of organizational citizenship behavior.
2. focusing on assuming leadership positions in the organization, which are characterized by the characteristics of transformational leaders, because of this positive impact on the orientation towards administrative empowerment.
3. Increasing leaders' awareness of the importance and consolidating the concept of a culture of administrative empowerment in order to raise the level of organizational citizenship behavior among employees.
4. The executive leaders in the organization should focus on practicing transformational leadership and administrative empowerment when facing crises and challenges, because transformational leadership and administrative empowerment are among the factors influencing organizational citizenship behavior.

Limitations and Suggestions

This study was conducted in the Yemen Red Sea Ports Corporation, so its results cannot be generalized to public or private sector organizations due to the influence of political, economic, and social factors on them, but the same model can be verified in those organizations.

Transformational leadership and administrative empowerment affect organizational citizenship behavior, while there are other variables that affect organizational citizenship behavior, such as organizational justice, job satisfaction, and organizational culture. Therefore, many studies could be conducted using more mediating and independent variables to support organizational citizenship behavior.

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